

Tracing the Development of Psychosocial Rehabilitation at the Central Institute of Psychiatry, Jharkhand

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Psychosocial rehabilitation (PSR) plays a crucial role in mental health care in India. The Central Institute of Psychiatry (CIP), Ranchi, a pioneer institute of Occupational Therapy (OT), 1922, which increased the quality of rehabilitation. PSR has different aspects, integrating skill enhancement by vocational training, therapeutic activities and the purpose is to reintegrate them in the mainstream of society. There is a very small amount of information available on psychosocial rehabilitation in CIP, though it has a significant history. This study will help to conceptualize the overall system of PSR in CIP and its functioning. It highlights the different vocational training programs, based on the needs of inpatients (both males & females). It describes the systematic transformation of PSR from the beginning to the advanced level. It can also show the engagement of the Psychiatric Social Work (PSW) department in PSR. Finally, the study highlights some scope for future improvement.

Keywords: Psychosocial rehabilitation (PSR), occupational therapy (OT) & social reintegration

Occupational therapy (OT) has evolved significantly over the past two centuries to support psychiatric recovery through structured activities. From the dormant stage, it plays a crucial role in mental health care and rehabilitation. The transition of Indian psychosocial rehabilitation from institutional care to community-based services is driven by legislative advancements and policy (Sundaram & Kumar, 2018). The Central Institute of Psychiatry (CIP) is a pioneer in rehabilitative services by introducing the structure of the Occupational Therapy Department in 1922. Though in 1920, the concept of Token Economy was evolved by its name of 'Habit Formation Chart' (Varma, 1953). Over a period of time, CIP has developed a comprehensive rehabilitation model encompassing skill assessment and vocational training, sheltered workshops, *Pahal* club and other psychosocial interventions. These initiatives aim to enhance patients' functional abilities, social integration and employability.

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Figure 1

Central Institute of Psychiatry

Some additional services like library, canteen (*Manokamana*) and structured remuneration systems based on work efficiency (unskilled, semiskilled and skilled) further support patient engagement. The introduction of new programs such as Product Demonstrations, *Punarvasan* Stall, cooking classes and Movie Screening has enriched the level of rehabilitation and also helped with patients' entertainment. The transformation of holistic care emphasizes skill acquisition, social participation and reintegration.

Method

This study employed an archival and descriptive institutional review design to document the development of psychosocial rehabilitation (PSR) services at the Central Institute of Psychiatry, Ranchi. Qualitative data were collected through institutional records, published reports, and historical documents related to the

Occupational Therapy (OT) and Psychiatric Social Work (PSW) departments. Primary data were gathered via face-to-face semi-structured interviews with OT in-charges and departmental employees, supplemented by focus group discussions, structured observation, case studies and product demonstration sessions to understand the practical functioning of the OT department. Photo-video elicitation and diary were additionally employed for documentation purposes. The triangulation of these methods enabled a comprehensive analysis of the development of PSR services, vocational training, and interdepartmental collaboration to enhance patient recovery outcomes.

Brief History of Psycho-Social Rehabilitation

India has a deep-rooted tradition of mental health care since the Vedic period, with treatments found in Charaka Samhitha, Sushruta Samhitha and Siddha texts using herbal methods. The concept of rehabilitation was built on that time which came before the Bethlem hospital in England (Raghavan et al., 2014). During the Tughluq dynasty, Firuz Shah Tughlaq built hospitals to detain mentally ill individuals (Kakunje et al., 2021).

The mental asylum was introduced in India in Bombay (1745), Calcutta (1787), Madras (1793), Chennai (1794), and Bihar (1795). In 1895, Rice introduced the concept of Occupational Therapy in India. The Mysore lunatic asylum pioneered 'Work Therapy', focusing on agriculture-based rehabilitation (Ponnuchamy, 2016). In 1918, the "Ranchi European Lunatic Asylum," currently named Central Institute of Psychiatry (CIP), was established. It was India's first Occupational Therapy Department, started in 1922 (Nizamie et al., 2008).

The Mental Health Act 1987 was the first legal framework outlining rights, admission and care for mentally ill persons. In 1992, the Rehabilitation Council of India (RCI) was established to regulate training and maintain a central rehabilitation register. In 1996, the District Mental Health Program (DMHP) was started under the National Mental Health Program (NMHP), 1982 was a landmark in expanding psychiatric care at the community level (Math et al., 2011).

In 2002, the Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment (GOI) introduced guidelines for disability certification using the Indian Disability Evaluation and Assessment Scale (IDEAS) for persons with mental illness (Kakunje et al., 2021). The Mental Healthcare Act, 2017, upholds the rights of persons with mental illness and mandates half-way homes, sheltered workshops and home-based rehabilitation to ensure privacy, dignity and quality of life.

Evolution of Psycho-social Rehabilitation at Central Institute of Psychiatry

The institute emphasized holistic psychiatric rehabilitation, offering nutritious meals, physical activities and different indoor-outdoor games like football, cricket, badminton, card games, chess and dominoes (Varma, 1953). Entertainment through music was encouraged and the asylum had its own Brass Band of 22 male attendants, which was led by an expert band master to entertain the staff and train the patients. Patients were assigned an Occupation Prescription and paid based on their performance to boost their motivation (Kakunje et al., 2021).

Stable patients could go outside the campus weekly with written consent. Family inclusive cottage wards were introduced in 1929 to

initiate Family therapy. In 1950, a Child Guidance Clinic was started, later evolving into the Centre for Child and Adolescent Psychiatry (CCAP) in 1975 (Nizamie et al., 2008). The child and adolescent are admitted with their guardians, participate in structured activities, including PT, indoor-outdoor games and Occupational Therapy as part of their behavioural management.

Chart 1

Structure of Psycho-social Rehabilitation, CIP

Note. (Source: CIP Institutional Records)

Male Occupational Therapy Unit

The Male OT unit provides structured, client-centered vocational training to enhance the functional abilities and overall well-being of individuals with mental health conditions. The attendance register is mandatory for the patients in each of the departments and they can share their areas of interest.

Carpentry Section: The Carpentry section was earlier crafted all wooden furniture for the hospital and hostel of CIP. Now it focuses on repairing old wooden items and handling special furniture projects based on requests from the authorities.

Blacksmith Section: This section trains the patients in basic metalwork. Currently, this section primarily focuses on repairing metal materials in response to requests and lacks engaging activities with the patients due to a shortage of necessary tools.

Figure 2

Male Occupational Therapy Unit

Painting Section: This section offers structured drawing classes for children, adolescents and adult patients, while stable patients participate in painting classes. Some selected art works are sold through a formal application to the director and a concerned committee determines a selling price and allows individuals to purchase.

Caning Section: In the caning section, patients are trained in both creating new chairs and repairing old ones, fostering practical skills in furniture making. Patients typically require about 7 to 10 days of training to develop the necessary techniques and they can work independently.

Weaving Section: This section offers training in both manual and semi-automatic weaving. Manual weaving classes are designed for both children and adult patients, where participants create doormats, while semi-automatic weaving classes are exclusively available for stable adult patients. Training duration varies between 10 to 15 days, depending on the individual's pace.

Rug Craft Section: Rug craft, which typically requires 3 to 4 months of training to master. For semi-skilled patients, the instructor first creates the structure of the rug and then involves them in the process.

Tailoring Section: This section trains patients in garment creation and design. The team primarily produces dresses and winter blazers for patients, tablecloths and window curtains based on requests from authorities. Interested patients receive hands-on training in tailoring skills under expert supervision.

Female Occupational Therapy Unit (OT)

The female OT unit managed by one head instructor and some specialised instructors, offers a range of specialized activities. For those interested in Knitting, Crochet, Stitching and Embroidery, guidance is provided by the instructors. Additionally, a cooking section offers opportunities for creative and functional skill development.

Skill Assessment Process: As part of psycho-social rehabilitation, a structured skill assessment process is followed using a Work Behaviour Assessment Score Sheet covering 12 domains. Patients are evaluated weekly and those scoring at least 50% of the total score (0 to 27) qualify for monetary incentives based on their skill level: Rs. 5/day for unskilled, Rs.15/Day for semi-skilled, and Rs. 20/day for skilled. The process is overseen by two committees, one for Skill Evaluation and the other for Work Evaluation.

Figure 3

Female Occupational Therapy Unit

Pahal Club: Pahal Club, under the brand name "PRERNA," serves as a platform for patient welfare through activities aimed at improving motor coordination and attention span. It offers indoor games such as carom, ludo and badminton for children. Children can access books, magazines, and daily newspapers on a regular basis. This therapeutic approach aids in restoring community functioning and enhances the well-being of individuals with psychiatric disabilities.

Sanitary Napkin Department: The Sanitary Napkin Department, located in Pinel Ward, is equipped with machines to produce sanitary pads for female patients. These are distributed to all female wards, the emergency ward, the RHC ward and the child ward in CIP. The unit operates under the Water Sanitation and Hygiene (WASH) initiative, with support from UNICEF and has been actively involved in CIP's Kayakalp Program.

D N Nandi Sheltered Workshop: This section originally provided vocational engagement for approximately 20 long-stay patients in bookbinding, reprography, creating case record forms, printing institutional forms and handles in binding for library journals. A Token Economy model was used to reinforce participation, where patients earn tokens exchangeable for snacks. During COVID-19 pandemic, patient engagement has decreased but the essential documents of the hospital like Case Record Files, prescriptions, bills, register books and envelopes for every department are printed from here.

Manokamna Canteen: The canteen offers therapeutic vocational engagement for selected patients who assist in various roles under staff supervision. The canteen operates from 9 am to 12 pm and from 2 pm to 4 pm, offering tea, biscuits and a variety of packaged foods to staff, students and patients. During admission, families can deposit money at the ward's nursing station; on that basis, they receive coupons from their respective wards to purchase food from the canteen. These coupons are used as positive reinforcement for patients to increase their behaviour in the ward.

Patient's Library: There are two patient libraries available in CIP, one for both male and female patients. It provides access to 11 newspapers and 13 magazines daily, along with a diverse collection of books. Patients can also enjoy various indoor and outdoor games, including badminton, chess, ludo, carrom board, table tennis, playing cards, volleyball and cricket. A regular music class is organized by a music teacher in both patients' libraries. Additionally, both the male and female libraries organize an annual sports event for the patients and staff of CIP.

Remuneration Process: The remuneration process of OT is a structured and motivating component for the patients. Patients who meet the minimum attendance requirements set by the work assessment committee are considered eligible for remuneration. Based on their skill classification- unskilled, semi-skilled and skilled the patients are categorized and their names forwarded for committee approval. Once approved, this list is sent to the accounts section for processing. Payments are generally disbursed either at the patient's discharge or during their follow-up.

- Engagement of Psychiatric Social Work (PSW) Dept. in Psychosocial Rehabilitation at CIP

Home Visit: Family is a very important part of psychiatry. So, to assess the family support or to corroborate the information of a patient's illness, CIP provides home visit facilities for some difficult cases. The main initiative is taken by the Department of PSW in

collaboration with the Clinical Psychology and Psychiatry department.

Awareness Program: The department of PSW participates in mental health-related awareness programs not only on the campus of CIP but also at different palaces in Jharkhand. The purpose of the program is to reduce social stigma towards mental illness.

Product Demonstration: An initiative is taken, where the creators share their experience and challenges while making a new product in OT. The respective ward in-charges also elaborated further to ensure that other patients could understand and appreciate the process.

Punarvasan Stall: A joint initiative is taken by the PSW Department, with the OT in charge. The main purpose of this stall is to sell handmade products made by the patients in CIP during Durga Pooja or National and International conferences at CIP.

Cooking Class: A monthly initiative is taken by the female OT in charge to collaborate with the PSW department, where the female patients prepare and distribute food under the supervision of female OT staffs. This therapeutic process can improve skills and cohesiveness among the patients.

Movie Screening: An entertainment activity organized by the OT staffs and the PSW Department. Movie screenings are held at the SS Hall in CIP, under staff supervision. Special screenings are held for children and adolescents of the CCAP ward on occasions like Children's Day and Autism Day.

Discussion

The strength of PSR lies in a diverse range of therapeutic and vocational activities, tailored to improve patients' functional abilities and foster their reintegration into society. The department, like carpentry, tailoring and weaving, demonstrates its commitment to skill-building and patient empowerment (Lloyd et al., 2008; Arbesman & Logsdon, 2011). The structured skill assessment and remuneration process helps to engage more patients' participation. The initiatives like the patients' library, Pahal Club and sheltered Workshop highlight how the patients are actively participating in the recreational activities, which is consistent with research showing that structured leisure and vocational activities improve functional outcomes in psychiatric rehabilitation (Leff & Warner, 2006). Some innovations in rehabilitation at CIP, like movie screening, Manokamna canteen, cooking class, product demonstration, games (indoor & outdoor) and Punarvasan Stall give them a chance of entertainment and increase skills, aligning with community reintegration principles emphasized in contemporary PSR frameworks (Anthony, 1993; Corrigan et al., 2008).

Despite these strengths, there are some areas for further improvement. First of all, there are a smaller number of studies found on Psychosocial Rehabilitation at CIP, which signifies the need for further study. The lack of proper supervision is also an important problem as staffs of the OT are experts and specialized in their own stream but not in Psychiatry and sometimes it creates challenges in dealing with emergencies faced by patients in OT. Material usage of some departments is decreasing, for instance, the blacksmith department, as the patients are not able to handle heavy machinery. Besides that, the tendency to use readymade cloth for the patients led to underutilization of tailoring machines.

The concept of Token Economy, which was highly effective during its initial phase, can increase patients' motivation towards OT. The Certification programs for regular participants and the enhancement of monetary allowances could also be beneficial. The PSR could be further extended in a way to liaise with different government or non-government organizations in terms of product selling, conduct workshops or any certification course. Finally, while PSR at CIP plays a pivotal role in addressing illness and implementing different therapeutic processes. The need for collaborative efforts, resource optimization and continuous evaluation to ensure sustainable improvements in patient care and rehabilitation outcomes.

Conclusion

Psychosocial rehabilitation is an essential approach to mental health care by focusing on individuals' capacity in social functioning, personal competencies and overall quality of life. This approach addresses the individual and their environment, moving beyond mere symptom management to promote social inclusion and community integration. Unlike traditional psychiatric treatments that often centre on medication and therapy, psychosocial rehabilitation emphasizes the development of skills necessary for everyday living and the cultivation of supportive social networks. Research indicates that early interventions targeting psychosocial factors such as social isolation, stigma and discrimination can lead to significant improvements in long-term outcomes for individuals with mental health disorders.

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